

NATIONAL BUREAU OF STATISTICS

Nigerian Domestic and Foreign Debt

(Q3 2019)

Report Date: January 2020

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Nigerian States and Federal Debt Stock data as at 30th September 2019 reflected that the country's total public debt portfolio stood at N26.14trn.

Further disaggregation of Nigeria's total public debt showed that N8.27trn or 31.55% of the debt was external while N17.94trn or 68.45% of the debt was domestic.

Similarly, total domestic debt was N4.04 trillion with Lagos state accounting for 10.9% of the total domestic debt stock while Yobe State has the least debt stock in this category with a contribution of 0.7% to the total domestic debt stock.

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 2,440 sq mi

Population: 3,616,382

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,609,616,667.34

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N7,912,596,332.05

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N68,003,077,437.81

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N69,351,518,272.18

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 14, 254 sq mi

Population: 4,111,706

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N23,261,208,811.40

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,014,807,850.67

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N95,219,782,086.14

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N95,604,743,892.60

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 2,734 sq mi

Population: 5,272,029

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N86,309,360,838.49

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N20,464,607,233.41

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N206,414,472,059.83

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N237,404,479,750.88

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 1,870 sq mi

Population: 5,356,592

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,163,231,045.41

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N6,073,241,006.13

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N33,431,158,600.07

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N34,007,803,458.86

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 18, 965 sq mi

Population: 6,286,719

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,508,713,547.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N8,268,708,138.19

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N97,502,601,723.17

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N105,197,691,087.92

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 8,150 sq mi

Population: 2,204,648

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N65,754,784,594.56

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,875,518,818.67

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N133,339,375,587.91

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N127,243,132,172.38

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 13,150 sq m

Population: 5,553,037

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,042,594,670.85

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N12,131,771,966.24

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N96,905,502,591.02

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N98,443,680,724.47

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 22, 316 sq mi

Population: 5,635,544

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N29,713,746,866.87

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N3,917,848,074.57

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N86,861,555,192.24

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N83,599,771,781.15

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 7,782 sq mi

Population: 3,741,838

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N17,236,760,150.47

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N16,731,425,493.77

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N168,819,230,129.37

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N167,967,705,888.45

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 6,833 sq mi

Population: 5,460,311

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N108,697,421,165.63

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N36,390,689,921.88

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N233,564,158,885.47

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N230,574,799,366.01

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 2,136 sq mi

Population: 2,791,167

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N21,377,703,339.77

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,140,599,994.92

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N42,053,162,874.44

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N44,664,873,336.95

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 6,873 sq mi

Population: 4,109,499

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N31,864,918,190.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N15,441,748,874.50

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N84,002,644,092.96

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N83,185,543,988.73

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 2,453 sq mi

Population: 3,157,552

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N19,970,750,042.13

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,054,605,377.85

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N86,905,756,443.45

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N85,694,711,527.42

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 2,765 sq mi

Population: 4,263,786

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,013,513,168.83

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N10,699,049,784.00

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N60,151,622,506.87

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N60,588,382,464.35

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 7, 246 sq mi

Population: 3,140,189

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N19,704,992,908.08

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N2,087,431,130.42

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N79,634,209,227.24

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N74,464,436,941.81

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 2,140 sq mi

Population: 5,214,833

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,862,451,370.69

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N10,550,388,151.30

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N148,598,063,157.77

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N148,900,627,563.76

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 8,940 sq mi

Population: 5,640,592

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N28,540,385,721.28

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,369,753,095.83

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N38,673,319,242.36

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N39,222,346,039.10

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 17,781 sq mi

Population: 7,976,735

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N32,375,805,354.07

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N22,401,973,458.00

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N97,264,280,664.14

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N90,444,405,270.87

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 7,773 sq mi

Population: 12,591,871

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N39,976,809,111.31

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N18,564,546,104.36

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N117,339,436,693.47

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N117,339,436,693.47

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 9,341 sq mi

Population: 7,569,751

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N30,600,344,094.58

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N4,807,071,081.00

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N66,164,163,901.64

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N66,164,163,901.64

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 14,200 sq mi

Population: 4,286,319

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,613,287,221.60

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N4,728,501,342.76

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N59,598,378,104.63

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N59,188,080,839.30

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 11,519 sq mi

Population: 4,324,074

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N24,975,272,155.83

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N6,683,808,064.70

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N105,135,912,916.85

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N123,436,748,898.43

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 14, 218 sq mi

Population: 3,086,249

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N20,589,752,212.98

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N16,090,373,542.93

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N61,335,531,821.69

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N63,177,349,538.89

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 1,381 sq mi

Population: 12,100,616

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N58,089,996,966.96

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N205,163,386,767.06

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N479,047,606,006.32

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N441,668,732,162.26

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 2,439,113

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N21,814,635,087.13

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N4,842,313,122.18

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N89,953,619,684.92

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N54,225,427,154.13

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 5,343,260

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N27,032,795,298.64

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N9,126,750,293.89

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N41,792,519,380.33

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N62,539,576,973.27

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 6,556.23 sq mi

Population: 5,024,191

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N18,491,242,908.33

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N29,583,479,438.84

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N95,174,172,678.30

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N140,993,426,875.02

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 6,000 sq mi

Population: 4,515,660

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N28,275,467,043.01

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N19,001,563,646.74

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N55,524,221,404.56

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N56,416,452,086.63

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 3,572 sq mi

Population: 4,536,877

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N10,094,358,181.86

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N10,205,102,028.94

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N144,804,503,035.23

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N141,792,935,913.24

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 10,986 sq mi

Population: 7,540,300

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N28,121,335,249.50

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N14,060,685,978.15

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N99,358,565,798.52

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N90,592,445,114.47

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 11, 936 sq mi

Population: 4,075,392

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N21,369,952,515.60

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N9,413,952,271.51

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N98,356,193,262.55

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N108,967,566,269.06

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 4,277 sq mi

Population: 7,023,942

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N75,843,269,695.71

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N75,974,536,695.99

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N266,936,225,793.65

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N266,936,225,793.65

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 10,028 sq mi

Population: 4,831,152

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,809,761,972.66

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N12,077,025,746.68

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N33,509,692,266.79

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N49,475,551,713.33

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 21, 032 sq mi

Population: 2,968,132

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N22,435,208,117.09

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N3,272,217,539.86

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N73,466,840,201.25

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N93,490,094,894.28

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 17, 568 sq mi

Population: 3,163,747

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,026,287,229.70

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N2,206,307,291.27

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N27,465,573,418.77

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N28,533,478,934.83

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N19,971,967,689.61

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N7,210,062,254.23

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N61,716,954,035.15

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N63,033,937,202.11

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N34,274,729,611.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N38,570,894,950.27

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N132,195,733,234.70

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N137,862,316,926.60

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2

N3,966,219,816,141.57

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3

N4,042,394,601,412.49

% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q3 2019

Important Notes

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty two (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q3 2019

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

FGN BONDS

PROMISSORY NOTES

FGN SAVINGS BOND

TOTAL

NIGERIAN TREASURY BONDS

FGN SUKUK

NIGERIAN TREASURY BILLS

GREEN BOND

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q3 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

PUBLIC DEBT STOCK - EXTERNAL AND DOMESTIC DEBT OF THE FGN, STATES AND FCT AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q3 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

PUBLIC DEBT STOCK - EXTERNAL AND DOMESTIC DEBT OF THE FGN, STATES AND FCT AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q3 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

GROWTH RATE %

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT ACTUAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR THIRD QUARTER, 2019 (AMOUNT IN NAIRA)

	July	August	Sept	Total
NTBs				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N18,658,359,984.10	N44,443,618,148.26	N41,478,337,656.63	N104,580,315,788.99
FGN Bonds				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N180,632,591,048.07	N124,984,282,051.18	N178,658,612,314.22	N484,275,485,413.47
Treasury Bonds				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N3,125,000,000.00	N3,125,000,000.00	N3,125,000,000.00	N9,375,000,000.00
FGN Savings Bond				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N123,019,799.08	N110,165,763.54	N102,441,547.37	N335,627,109.99
FGN SUKUK				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	-----	-----	N8,302,684,931.51	N8,302,684,931.51
FGN Green Bond				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	-----	-----	-----	-----
TOTAL INTEREST				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N202,538,970,831.25	N172,663,065,962.98	N231,667,076,449.72	N606,869,113,243.96

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q3 2019

DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR THIRD QUARTER, 2019

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT ACTUAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR APRIL - JUNE, 2019 (AMOUNT IN NAIRA)

Category	April	May	June	Total
NTBs	Interest N14,897,947,747.19	Interest N14,700,317,313.85	Interest N16,113,483,121.45	Interest N45,711,748,182.49
FGN Bonds	Interest N69,184,981,715.55	Interest N31,779,137,060.69	Interest N28,027,002,739.73	Interest N128,991,121,515.97
Treasury Bonds	Interest -----	Interest N3125000000	Interest N3125000000	Interest N6,250,000,000.00
FGN Savings Bond	Interest N112,381,123.27	Interest N100,208,236.88	Interest N98,031,264.55	Interest N310,620,624.70
FGN SUKUK	Interest -----	Interest -----	Interest N7849934247	Interest N7,849,934,246.58
FGN Green Bond	Interest -----	Interest -----	Interest N718532011	Interest N718,532,010.96
TOTAL INTEREST	Interest N84,195,310,586.01	Interest N49,704,662,611.42	Interest N55,931,983,383.27	Interest N189,831,956,580.70

PERCENTAGE CHANGE OF INTEREST PAYMENT IN DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE Q3 & Q2, 2019

Total

\$134,383.69

MULTILATERAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$72,820.32	\$35,673.28	\$22,548.91	-----	\$963.00	\$215.63	-----	\$(89.34)	\$1,751.89	\$500.00

IBRD

Total

\$6,354.35

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$5,868.73	0.00	0.00	\$485.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

A.D.B

Total

\$26,122.75

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$10,000.00	\$15,747.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$375.00

IFAD

Total

\$8,919.28

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$6,292.87	\$2,482.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$143.84	0.00

A.D.F

Total **\$1,996.08** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$1,633.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$362.22	0.00

AGTF

Total **\$200.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$75.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$125.00

IDA

Total **\$89,693.40** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$55,543.37	\$9,781.51	\$22,548.91	0.00	\$447.49	\$215.63	0.00	-\$89.34	\$1,245.83	0.00

EDF

Total **\$1,097.82** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$984.08	\$83.86	0.00	0.00	\$29.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

BADEA

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

IDB

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total
\$76,519.86

BILATERAL

Percentage of Total **16.15%**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$34,596.15	\$39,195.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	\$(0.28)	\$2,724.44	\$4.37

EXIM BANK OF CHINA

Total **\$72,076.08** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$34,596.15	\$34,819.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$2,660.93	0.00

NIGERIA COMMUNICATION SATELLITE

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA NATIONAL PUBLIC SECURITY COMM. SYS. PROJECT

Total **\$19,881.10** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$15,365.38	\$4,515.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (IDU KADUNA SECTION)

Total **\$24,882.48** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$19,230.77	\$5,651.71	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (LAGOS - IBADAN SECTION)

Total **\$7,811.71** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$6,668.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$1,142.97	0.00

NIGERIA ABUJA LIGHT RAIL PROJECT

Total **\$5,930.99** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$5,891.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$39.82	0.00

NIGERIA ICT INFRASTRUCTURE BACKBONE PROJECT

Total **\$1,241.74** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$1,238.61	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$3.13	0.00

NIGERIA FOUR AIRPORT TERMINALS EXPANSION PROJECT

Total **\$5,222.85** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$5,121.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$101.39	0.00

NIGERIAN ZUNGERU HYDROELECTRIC PROJECT

Total **\$5,625.58** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$4,853.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$772.43	0.00

NIGERIAN REHABILITATION AND UPGRADING OF ABUJA-KEFFI-MAKURDI ROAD PROJECT

Total **\$1,479.62** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$878.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$601.18	0.00

EXIM BANK OF INDIA

Total **\$349.96** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$279.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$70.18	0.00

FRENCH DEVELOPMENT AGENCY

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

JICA

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

KFW

Total **\$4,093.82** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$4,096.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$-0.28	\$-6.67	\$4.37

Total

\$263,036.25

Percentage of Total

COMMERCIAL

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$263,036.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$263,036.25

Percentage of Total

EUROBONDS

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$263,036.25	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

5.125% EUROBOND 2018

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

6.75% EUROBOND 2021

Total **\$16,875.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$16,875.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

6.375% EUROBOND 2023

Total **\$15,940.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$15,940.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2032

Total **\$59,062.50** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$59,062.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.625% EUROBOND 2047

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

6.5% EUROBOND 2027

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.625% EUROBOND 2025

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

8.747% EUROBOND 2031

Total **\$43,735.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$43,735.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.696% EUROBOND 2038

Total **\$48,100.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$48,100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

9.248% EUROBOND 2049

Total **\$34,680.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$34,680.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.143% EUROBOND 2030

Total **\$44,643.75** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$44,643.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

0.00

DIASPORA BOND

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

5.625% DIASPORA BOND 2022

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

0.00

OTHERS

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

AGENCY FEES

Total

0.00

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

OIL WARRANT

Total

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$473,939.80

TOTAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest
\$107,416.48	\$337,904.70	\$22,548.91	0.00	\$963.00
Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$215.63	0.00	\$(89.61)	\$4,476.33	\$504.37

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q3 2019

NIGERIA'S EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

('million)

MULTILATERAL

BILATERAL

('million)

COMMERCIAL

EUROBONDS

\$10,868.35

40.34%

DIASPORA BOND

\$300.00

1.11%

Sub-Total

\$11,168.35

SUB - TOTAL

Percentage of Total

GRAND TOTAL

\$26,941.50

Percentage of Total

METHODOLOGY

Data is supplied administratively by the Debt Management Office, Nigeria and verified and validated by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria.

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

Table I: Public Debt Stock - External and Domestic Debt of the FGn, States and FCT as at September 30, 2019

Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M)	Amount Outstanding (N'M)	% of Total
Total External Debt	26,941.50	8,271,040.50	31.55%
FGN Only	22,666.83	6,958,716.81	26.54%
States & FCT	4,274.67	1,312,323.69	5.01%
Total Domestic Debt	58,449.32	17,943,940.63	68.45%
FGN Only	45,281.91	13,901,546.03	53.03%
States & FCT	13,167.41	4,042,394.60	15.42%
Total Public Debt(A+B)	85,390.82	26,214,981.13	100%

Public Debt Stock - External and Domestic Debt of the FGn, States and FCT as at June 30, 2019					Analysis of Percentage Increase of Nigeria's Public Debt Q3 & Q2, 2019	
Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M)	Amount Outstanding (N'M)	% of Total	USD	NGN	
A.	Total External Debt	27,162.63	8,322,629.83	32.38%	-0.81%	-0.62%
	FGN Only	22,887.96	7,012,870.94	27.29%	-0.97%	-0.77%
	States & FCT	4,274.67	1,309,758.89	5.10%	0.00%	0.20%
B.	Total Domestic Debt	56,720.03	17,379,015.91	67.62%	3.05%	3.25%
	FGN Only	43,775.44	13,412,796.09	52.19%	3.44%	3.64%
	States & FCT	12,944.58	3,966,219.82	15.43%	1.72%	1.92%
C.	Total Public Debt(A+B)	83,882.66	25,701,645.74	100%	1.80%	2.00%
					NOTE: Variation in the growth rate is due to exchange rate variations within the periods	

Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty-one (31) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto Taraba, Yobe and Zamafara) and FCT were as at June 30, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for Four (4) States, (Anambra, Bayelsa, Benue, and Nassarawa) were as at March 31, 2019 and the Domestic Debt Stock Figure for Rivers State was as at December 31, 2018.

CBN Official Exchange Rate of US\$1 to NGN307 as at September 30, 2019 was used in converting External Debt to Naira

Federal Government Domestic Debt Stock by Instrument as at September 30, 2019

Instruments	Amounts in Naira	% Share of each Debt Instrument
FGN Bonds	10,074,909,394,592.00	72.47%
FGN Savings Bond	10,793,404,000.00	0.08%
FGN Sukuk	200,000,000,000.00	1.44%
Green Bond	25,690,000,000.00	0.18%
Nigerian Treasury Bills	2,651,514,042,000.00	19.07%
Nigerian Treasury Bonds	125,988,000,000.00	0.91%
Promissory Notes	812,651,186,786.00	5.85%
TOTAL	13,901,546,027,378.00	100.00%

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019

AMOUNT IN NAIRA					PROVISIONAL	
SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK AS AT Q3	DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2	DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2	% CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q3 & Q2	% Share of each State to Total Debt Stock, Q3 2019
1	ABIA	69,351,518,272.18	68,003,077,437.81		2.0%	1.7%
2	ADAMAWA	95,604,743,892.60	95,219,782,086.14		0.4%	2.4%
3	AKWA IBOM	237,404,479,750.88	206,414,472,059.83		15.0%	5.9%
4	ANAMBRA	34,007,803,458.86	33,431,158,600.07		1.7%	0.8%
5	BAUCHI	105,197,691,087.92	97,502,601,723.17		7.9%	2.6%
6	BAYELSA	127,243,132,172.38	133,339,375,587.91		-4.6%	3.1%
7	BENUE	98,443,680,724.47	96,905,502,591.02		1.6%	2.4%
8	BORNO	83,599,771,781.15	86,861,555,192.24		-3.8%	2.1%
9	CROSS-RIVER	167,967,705,888.45	168,819,230,129.37		-0.5%	4.2%
10	DELTA	230,574,799,366.01	233,564,158,885.47		-1.3%	5.7%
11	EBONYI	44,664,873,336.95	42,053,162,874.44		6.2%	1.1%
12	EDO	83,185,543,988.73	84,002,644,092.96		-1.0%	2.1%
13	EKITI	85,694,711,527.42	86,905,756,443.45		-1.4%	2.1%
14	ENUGU	60,588,382,464.35	60,151,622,506.87		0.7%	1.5%
15	GOMBE	74,464,436,941.81	79,634,209,227.24		-6.5%	1.8%
16	IMO	148,900,627,563.76	148,598,063,157.77		0.2%	3.7%
17	JIGAWA	39,222,346,039.10	38,673,319,242.36		1.4%	1.0%
18	KADUNA	90,444,405,270.87	97,264,280,664.14		-7.0%	2.2%
19	KANO	117,339,436,693.47	117,339,436,693.47		0.0%	2.9%
20	KATSINA	66,164,163,901.64	66,164,163,901.64		0.0%	1.6%
21	KEBBI	59,188,080,839.30	59,598,378,104.63		-0.7%	1.5%
22	KOGI	123,436,748,898.43	105,135,912,916.85		17.4%	3.1%
23	KWARA	63,177,349,538.89	61,335,531,821.69		3.0%	1.6%
24	LAGOS	441,668,732,162.26	479,047,606,006.32		-7.8%	10.9%
25	NASARAWA	54,225,427,154.13	89,953,619,684.92		-39.7%	1.3%
26	NIGER	62,539,576,973.27	41,792,519,380.33		49.6%	1.5%
27	OGUN	140,993,426,875.02	95,174,172,678.30		48.1%	3.5%
28	ONDO	56,416,452,086.63	55,524,221,404.56		1.6%	1.4%
29	OSUN	141,792,935,913.24	144,804,503,035.23		-2.1%	3.5%
30	OYO	90,592,445,114.47	99,358,565,798.52		-8.8%	2.2%
31	PLATEAU	108,967,566,269.06	98,356,193,262.55		10.8%	2.7%
32	RIVERS	266,936,225,793.65	266,936,225,793.65		0.0%	6.6%
33	SOKOTO	49,475,551,713.33	33,509,692,266.79		47.6%	1.2%
34	TARABA	93,490,094,894.28	73,466,840,201.25		27.3%	2.3%
35	YOBE	28,533,478,934.83	27,465,573,418.77		3.9%	0.7%
36	ZAMFARA	63,033,937,202.11	61,716,954,035.15		2.1%	1.6%
37	FCT	137,862,316,926.60	132,195,733,234.70		4.3%	3.4%
Total		4,042,394,601,412.49	3,966,219,816,141.57		1.9%	100%
Important Notes						
1	Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (32) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and FCT as at September 30, 2019					
2	Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Three (3) States, (Bayelsa, Kano and Kastina) were as at June 30, 2019					
3	Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at December 30, 2018					

**FEDERAL GOVERNMENT ACTUAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE
FOR THIRD QUARTER, 2019 (AMOUNT IN NAIRA)**

Instruments	July	August	September	Total
NTBs				
Interest	18,658,359,984.10	44,443,618,148.26	41,478,337,656.63	104,580,315,788.99
Federal Govt. Bonds				
Interest	180,632,591,048.07	124,984,282,051.18	178,658,612,314.22	484,275,485,413.47
Treasury Bonds				
Interest	3,125,000,000.00	3,125,000,000.00	3,125,000,000.00	9,375,000,000.00
Principal	-	-	-	-
FGNSB				
Interest	123,019,799.08	110,165,763.54	102,441,547.37	335,627,109.99
FGN Sukuk				
Interest	-	-	8,302,684,931.51	8,302,684,931.51
FGN Green Bond				
Interest	-	-	-	-
TOTAL INTEREST	202,538,970,831.25	172,663,065,962.98	231,667,076,449.72	606,869,113,243.96

**FEDERAL GOVERNMENT ACTUAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE
FOR APRIL - JUNE, 2019 (AMOUNT IN NAIRA)**

Instruments	April	May	June	Total	% Change of Interest Payment in Domestic Debt Service Q3 & Q2, 2019
NTBs					
Interest	14,897,947,747.19	14,700,317,313.85	16,113,483,121.45	45,711,748,182.49	128.8%
Federal Govt. Bonds					
Interest	69,184,981,715.55	31,779,137,060.69	28,027,002,739.73	128,991,121,515.97	275.4%
Treasury Bonds					
Interest	-	3125000000	3125000000	6,250,000,000.00	50.0%
Principal	-	-	-	-	
FGNSB					
Interest	112,381,123.27	100,208,236.88	98,031,264.55	310,620,624.70	8.1%
FGN SUKUK					
Interest	-	-	7849934247	7,849,934,246.58	5.8%
FGN Green Bond					
Interest	-	-	718532011	718,532,010.96	
TOTAL INTEREST	84,195,310,586.01	49,704,662,611.42	55,931,983,383.27	189,831,956,580.70	219.7%

**NIGERIA'S EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2019
IN MILLIONS OF USD**

Category	Outstanding Debt	Percentage Share of each Category to Total
MULTILATERAL		
World Bank Group		
IDA	9,405.58	34.91%
IBRD	409.51	1.52%
African Development Bank Group		
ADB	1,366.26	5.07%
AGTF	-	0.00%
ADF	903.38	3.35%
BADEA	5.88	0.02%
EDF	54.99	0.20%
IDB	14.65	0.05%
IFAD	182.92	0.68%
SUB-TOTAL	12,343.17	45.81%
BILATERAL		
China (Exim Bank of China)	2,746.92	10.20%
France (AFD)	365.50	1.36%
Japan (JICA)	76.52	0.28%
India (Exim Bank of India)	29.59	0.11%
Germany (KFW)	211.45	0.78%
SUB-TOTAL	3,429.98	12.73%
COMMERCIAL		
EUROBONDS	10,868.35	40.34%
DIASPORA BOND	300.00	1.11%
SUB-TOTAL	11,168.35	41.45%
GRAND TOTAL	26,941.50	100.00%

NIGERIA'S ACTUAL EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE PAYMENTS IN THIRD QUARTER, 2019 IN THOUSANDS OF USD

Category	Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/ Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges	Total	Percentage of Total
MULTILATERAL	72,820.32	35,673.28	22,548.91	-	963.00	215.63	-	(89.34)	1,751.89	500.00	134,383.69	28.35%
IBRD	0.00	5,868.73	0.00	0.00	485.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6,354.35	
A.D.B	10,000.00	15,747.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	375.00	26,122.75	
IFAD	6,292.87	2,482.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	143.84	0.00	8,919.28	
A.D.F	0.00	1,633.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	362.22	0.00	1,996.08	
AGTF	0.00	75.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	125.00	200.00	
IDA	55,543.37	9,781.51	22,548.91	0.00	447.49	215.63	0.00	-89.34	1,245.83	0.00	89,693.40	
EDF	984.08	83.86	0.00	0.00	29.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,097.82	
BADEA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDB	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
BILATERAL	34,596.15	39,195.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	(0.28)	2,724.44	4.37	76,519.86	16.15%
EXIM Bank of China	34,596.15	34,819.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2,660.93	0.00	72,076.08	
Nigeria Communication Sattellite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria National Public Security Comm. Sys. Project	15,365.38	4,515.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	19,881.10	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Idu Kaduna Section)	19,230.77	5,651.71	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	24,882.48	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Lagos - Ibadan Section)	0.00	6,668.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,142.97	0.00	7,811.71	
Nigeria Abuja Light Rail Project	0.00	5,891.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.82	0.00	5,930.99	
Nigeria ICT Infrastructure Backbone Project	0.00	1,238.61	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.13	0.00	1,241.74	
Nigeria Four Airport Terminals Expansion Project	0.00	5,121.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	101.39	0.00	5,222.85	
Nigerian Zungeru Hydroelectric Project	0.00	4,853.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	772.43	0.00	5,625.58	
Nigerian Rehabilitation and Upgrading of Abuja-Keffi-Makurdi Road Project	0.00	878.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	601.18	0.00	1,479.62	
EXIM Bank of India	0.00	279.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.18	0.00	349.96	
French Development Agency	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
JICA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
KFW	0.00	4,096.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.28	-6.67	4.37	4,093.82	
COMMERCIAL	0.00	263,036.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	263,036.25	55.50%
EUROBONDS	0.00	263,036.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	263,036.25	
5.125% Eurobond 2018	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.75% Eurobond 2021	0.00	16,875.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16,875.00	
6.375% Eurobond 2023	0.00	15,940.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15,940.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2032	0.00	30,021.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30,021.25	
7.625% Eurobond 2017	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.5% Eurobond 2017	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.625% Eurobond 2015	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.375% Eurobond 2011	0.00	43,750.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	43,750.00	
7.88% Eurobond 2011	0.00	41,100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	41,100.00	
9.28% Eurobond 2011	0.00	34,000.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34,000.00	
7.145% Eurobond 2011	0.00	44,643.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	44,643.75	
SHAFRWA BOND	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.687% Singapore Bond 2012	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OTHERS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00%
Agency Fees	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OIL WARRANT	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	
TOTAL	107,416.48	337,904.70	22,548.91	0.00	963.00	215.63	0.00	(89.61)	4,476.33	504.37	473,939.80	100%

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS/CONTACTS

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the contributions of our strategic partner Debt Management Office, Nigeria and our technical partner, Proshare in the design, concept and production of this publication.

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